

Motivation of the experiment:

In order to proof the sensitivity of our setup towards changes of water content in the tested material, we measured sheets of filter paper containing variable amounts of water. We chose filter paper as a reference material (or artificial leaf) as the water content of the samples can be controlled with high precision.

This setup is thought to provide a proof of the concept we applied in the manuscript. However, emissivity and evaporation properties of filter paper and plant leaves are not identical. Therefore, we expected that a quantitative confirmation of the model presented in the manuscript will not be possible. Still, filter paper was our reference material of choice, as – to our knowledge – there is no alternative material resembling plant leaf properties more accurately.

Material & Methods

The temperature of the water used for wetting the filter papers was kept at 22°C using a water bath. Different volumes of water (0, 1200, 1500, 2500 μl) were added to round filter papers (area = 95 cm^2) by pipetting the water on the center of the paper. 1200 μl showed to be the minimum amount of water allowing an even distribution of the water within the filter paper. After homogenous distribution of the added water, samples were transferred into the experimental setup as described in the manuscript. After one minute of acclimation, a sequence of 950 frames was recorded (5 frames/second). Heat pulses were applied after approx. 50, 350, and 650 frames, resulting in capturing three separate cooling curves. For further analysis, these three curves were pooled and considered as one replicate. Per concentration (0, 12.6, 15.8, 26.3 $\mu\text{l}/\text{cm}^2$) three replicates were measured in a randomized sequence. The maximum temperature at the end of each single heat pulse was set as Temperature₀ (T_0) and time₀ (t_0), the absolute temperature decrease after the heat pulse was calculated for 200 frames following t_0 .

Results/Discussion

As shown in Figure 1, the water content of the filter papers had a strong influence on the resulting cooling curves. The amplitude of ΔT decreases with increasing water content. Also the cooling per time $\Delta T/\Delta t$ is negatively correlated with the water content, as reflected by the slope of the cooling curves. These two effects can be attributed to the increased total heat capacity of the filter papers caused by the additional water per area.

By normalizing the cooling curves (Fig. 2, $T_0 = 0$ and $T_{\text{min}} = -1$) it becomes obvious that the relative cooling per time does not depend on differences in water content. Only dry filter samples showed an increased relative ΔT . As the exchange of heat from dry filter paper runs much more effective than from the water/paper body to the environment, dry filter paper reaches the equilibrium much faster (Fig. 1). On the other hand, samples of all three water concentrations reached the equilibrium at approximately the same time. As mentioned above the absolute cooling rate is a function of the water content, hence the relative cooling rate remained stable.

In plant leaves the rate of heat transfer is much more complex than in the case of filter paper, particularly due to stomatal regulation and heterogeneous leaf structure, both affecting the boundary layer and the efficiency of heat exchange. As a consequence, the relative cooling rate is not constant, in most cases even in leaves with similar water content. This explains why it is extremely difficult to find a proper material for establishing artificial leaves.

In conclusion, we confirmed that we are able to detect differences in water content reliably (proof of concept). We conclude that an in-depth validation of the model presented in the manuscript is not possible with known artificial materials.

Figure 1. Cooling curves of differently wetted filter papers (0, 12.6, 15.8 or 26.3 $\mu\text{l cm}^{-2}$). The temperature change after application of the heat pulse (ΔT) was measured for 40 s after switching off the heating units. Mean \pm SD, n=3.

Figure 2. Cooling curves of differently wetted filter papers (0, 12.6, 15.8 or 26.3 $\mu\text{l cm}^{-2}$). The relative temperature change after application of the heat pulse (ΔT) was measured for 40 s after switching off the heating units. Mean \pm SD, n=3.